

EGA Submission Guide: Clinical Data

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Background

Clinical data describes participants' characteristics (e.g., gender), health status (e.g., diseases), treatments (e.g., chemotherapy), outcomes (e.g., survival), etc, associated with biological samples (e.g., a blood sample).

Clinical data is submitted as structured, de-identified datasets. In the absence of direct 'participant' representation in the EGA, this data is linked to samples.

For more information about de-identified datasets and working with sensitive data, please refer to the following resources:

- [Webinar recording: Working with Sensitive Data](#)

The purpose of this guide is to support users with their submissions of clinical data within the current EGA metadata framework ([EGA v1 metadata model](#)). As described in the instructions below, the workflow primarily involves programmatic submission of XML files through the [Webin API](#), alongside the use of the [Webin User Interface](#) for selected submission steps where applicable.

Before You Start

Before preparing your submission, ensure that:

- You have an EGA submission account (ega-box)
- Clinical data has been de-identified
- Participant identifiers have been pseudonymized
- A data dictionary has been prepared
- Participant identifiers can be linked to EGA samples
- Appropriate consent is in place for data sharing

Required Files

1. Clinical Data File

- File containing de-identified participant-level clinical variables.
- Format: `.csv`
- One row = one participant
- One column = one variable

Example:

```
participant_id,age,sex,disease,phenotype,treatment_group,bmi,outcome  
P001,45,F,Breast cancer,HP:0003002,Drug_A,24.5,improved  
P002,60,M,Breast cancer,HP:0003002,Drug_B,27.1,stable
```

2. Data Dictionary File

- Data dictionary describing the variables included in the clinical data file. Providing definitions, formats, and allowed values for each participant-level variable.
- Format: `.csv`
- Required file describing all variables
- Should match Clinical Data File headers exactly

Example:

```
variable,description,values_or_units  
participant_id,Unique pseudonymized participant identifier,String  
(e.g., P001)  
age,Age at diagnosis,Years  
sex,Biological sex,M/F  
phenotype,Phenotypic feature,HP0 term (e.g., HP:0003002)  
outcome,Treatment outcome,improved/stable/worsened
```

Decide How to Organize Your Clinical Data

Clinical data must support participant withdrawal and can be submitted using two different approaches.

Option A: Single Clinical Data File

Recommended for:

- Small to medium studies
- Stable datasets
- Infrequent consent withdrawals

Structure:

All Samples included in one analysis

```
Study
├── Samples
│   └── Analysis
│       ├── clinical_data.csv
│       └── data_dictionary.csv
```

Advantages:

- Simpler submission
- Fewer files to manage

Limitations:

- Entire file must be replaced when participants withdraw consent

Option B: One Clinical Data File per Participant

Recommended for:

- Longitudinal cohorts
- Studies with frequent participant withdrawals
- Automated submission workflows

Structure:

Two Analysis Per Sample

```
STUDY
├── SAMPLE A ( Participant A)
│   ├── ANALYSIS A
│   │   └── clinical_data_A.csv
│   └── SAMPLE B ( Participant B)
│       ├── ANALYSIS B
│       │   └── clinical_data_B.csv
└── SAMPLE A + Sample B
    ├── ANALYSIS A+B
    │   └── data_dictionary.csv
```

Advantages:

- Easier participant removal
- Better traceability
- No large file replacements

Limitations:

- More files
- More metadata objects

How to Submit Clinical Data

Submission Overview

Scope of This Guide

All submissions to the EGA require the registration of the following [metadata objects](#):

- **Study**
- **Samples**
- **Runs (Experiments) and/or Analyses**
- **Dataset**
- **Policy**
- **Data Access Committee (DAC)**

This guide focuses specifically on the submission of **clinical data**, and therefore provides detailed guidance on the most relevant metadata objects for this purpose:

- **Study** (context of the project)
- **Samples** (used to represent participants and enable linkage)
- **Analysis** (used to submit clinical data files under controlled access)

For guidance on how to register the remaining required objects—**Dataset, Data Access Policy, and DAC**—please refer to the official submission documentation via → [How to submit to the WEBIN?](#)

Samples and Participants

In the [EGA metadata model](#), a **sample** typically represents a biological specimen. However, for clinical data submissions, the term *sample* is often used to refer to the **participant**. The [sample_alias](#) used during sample registration should correspond directly to the de-identified [participant_id](#) in the clinical data file. The term *sample* conceptually represents an individual in this context.

Submission Workflow

1. Set Submission Account
 - a. Register a [EGA submission Account](#) (ega-box)

2. Upload datafiles (i.e. clinical data file(s) & data dictionary)
 - a. Encrypt the files with the [EGAcryptor tool](#)
 - b. Upload the files to the EGA using [FTP protocol](#)

3. Register the metadata
 - a. Register Study
 - The registration of the study can be done through the [WEBIN UI](#) or the [WEBIN API](#)
 - Obtain a **Study accession** (e.g., [EGAS00001001111](#))
 - b. Register Samples
 - The registration of the samples can be done through the [WEBIN UI](#) or the [WEBIN API](#)

Requirements:

 - One sample per participant
 - Use pseudonymized identifiers¹
 - [participant_id](#) in clinical data file must match [sample_alias](#)
 - Obtain the **Sample accession(s)** (e.g., [EGAN00001001111](#))
 - c. Register Runs (Optional)
 - Only if human sequencing data is included
 - Link runs to the correct samples

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<https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/data-sharing/anonymisation/pseudonymisation>

d. Register Analyses (Clinical Data)

For Clinical Data, **two files are required to register through analysis:**

1. Clinical data file
2. Data dictionary file

Clinical data file:

This analysis represents the main clinical phenotype data file.

Analysis-level attributes

Attribute	Value
ANALYSIS_TYPE	SAMPLE_PHENOTYPE

File-level attributes

Attribute	Value
File format	.csv
FILE_TYPE	phenotype_file

Data Dictionary file:

Analysis-level attributes

Attribute	Value
ANALYSIS_TYPE	SAMPLE_PHENOTYPE

File-level attributes

Attribute	Value
File format	.csv
FILE_TYPE	info

Clinical data files metadata must be submitted as [ANALYSIS objects](#). To submit an Analysis object, you must create **two XML files**:

XML	Purpose
Analysis XML	Describes your data and files
Submission XML	Tells WEBIN how to process this submission

More information: [How to submit analysis?](#)

- Choose the XML example that matches your selected submission strategy:
 - Option A XML (single file)
 - Option B XML (one file per participant)

 Option A: **Analysis XML** (`analysis.xml`) Example

Use this approach when you have one clinical phenotype file covering multiple samples and a single data dictionary describing the variables included in that file. Both files are linked within the same analysis object and associated with all relevant samples.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<ANALYSIS_SET>
  <ANALYSIS alias="Clinical_Data"
            analysis_center="XXXX"
            analysis_date="202X-0X-08T00:00:00">

    <TITLE>Clinical Data and Data Dictionary</TITLE>

    <DESCRIPTION>
      Clinical dataset describing participant demographics,
      disease characteristics, and outcomes, together with the
      associated data dictionary providing definitions, formats,
      units, and allowed values for each participant-level variable.
    </DESCRIPTION>

    <STUDY_REF accession="EGAS00001001111"/>

    <SAMPLE_REF accession="EGAN00001001111"/>
    <SAMPLE_REF accession="EGAN00001001112"/>
    <SAMPLE_REF accession="EGAN00001001113"/>

    <ANALYSIS_TYPE>
      <SAMPLE_PHENOTYPE/>
    </ANALYSIS_TYPE>

    <FILES>
      <FILE
        filename="clinical_data_all_samples.csv"
        filetype="phenotype_file"
        checksum_method="MD5"

        unencrypted_checksum="ff9dd3a61d88092cb74ff82270000000"
        checksum="ff9dd3a61d88092cb74ff82270000000" />

      <FILE
        filename="data_dictionary.csv"
        filetype="info"
        checksum_method="MD5"

        unencrypted_checksum="ff9dd3a61d88092cb74ff82270000000000"
```

```
checksum="ff9dd3a61d88092cb74ff8227000000000" />  
</FILES>  
  
</ANALYSIS>  
  
</ANALYSIS_SET>
```

 Option B: **Analysis XML** (`analysis.xml`) Example

Use this approach when clinical data are provided in multiple files, for example one file per participant. Each clinical file is represented as a separate analysis and linked to the corresponding sample. The data dictionary is submitted as an independent analysis describing the variables used across the phenotype datasets.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<ANALYSIS_SET>
  <ANALYSIS alias="Clinical_data_A" analysis_center="XXXX"
analysis_date="202X-0X-08T00:00:00">
    <TITLE>Clinical Data</TITLE>
    <DESCRIPTION>Clinical dataset describing participant
demographics, disease, and outcomes</DESCRIPTION>
    <STUDY_REF accession="EGAS00001001111"/>
    <SAMPLE_REF accession="EGAN00001001111"/>
    <ANALYSIS_TYPE>
      <SAMPLE_PHENOTYPE/>
    </ANALYSIS_TYPE>
    <FILES>
      <FILE filename="clinical_data_A.csv"
filetype="phenotype_file" checksum_method="MD5"
unencrypted_checksum="ff9dd3a61d88092cb74ff82270000000"
checksum="ff9dd3a61d88092cb74ff82270000000"/>
    </FILES>
  </ANALYSIS>
  <ANALYSIS alias="Clinical_data_B" analysis_center="XXXX"
analysis_date="202X-0X-08T00:00:00">
    <TITLE>Clinical Data</TITLE>
    <DESCRIPTION>Clinical dataset describing participant
demographics, disease, and outcomes</DESCRIPTION>
    <STUDY_REF accession="EGAS00001001111"/>
    <SAMPLE_REF accession="EGAN00001001112"/>
    <ANALYSIS_TYPE>
      <SAMPLE_PHENOTYPE/>
    </ANALYSIS_TYPE>
    <FILES>
      <FILE filename="clinical_data_B.csv"
filetype="phenotype_file" checksum_method="MD5"
unencrypted_checksum="ff9dd3a61d88092cb74ff82270000000"
checksum="ff9dd3a61d88092cb74ff82270000000"/>
    </FILES>
  </ANALYSIS>
  <ANALYSIS alias="Data_Dictionary" analysis_center="XXXX">
```

```
analysis_date="202X-0X-0XT00:00:00">
  <TITLE>Data Dictionary for Clinical Data</TITLE>
  <DESCRIPTION>Data dictionary describing the variables included
in the clinical phenotype dataset,
  providing definitions, formats, units, and allowed values for
each participant-level variable.</DESCRIPTION>
  <STUDY_REF accession="EGAS00001001111" />
  <SAMPLE_REF accession="EGAN00001001111" />
  <SAMPLE_REF accession="EGAN00001001112" />
  <ANALYSIS_TYPE>
    <SAMPLE_PHENOTYPE />
  </ANALYSIS_TYPE>
  <FILES>
    <FILE filename="data_dictionary.csv" filetype="info"
checksum_method="MD5"
unencrypted_checksum="ff9dd3a61d88092cb74ff8227000000000"
checksum="ff9dd3a61d88092cb74ff8227000000000" />
  </FILES>
</ANALYSIS>
</ANALYSIS_SET>
```

Submission XML (submission.xml) Example

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<SUBMISSION_SET xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
xsi:noNamespaceSchemaLocation="SRA.submission.xsd">
  <SUBMISSION alias="Example!_Clinical_Data_1" center_name="XXXX"
broker_name="EGA">
    <ACTIONS>
      <ACTION>
        <ADD source="analysis.xml" schema="analysis"/>
      </ACTION>
      <ACTION>
        <PROTECT/>
        <!-- ALL EGA SUBMISSIONS SHOULD HAVE THE PROTECT ACTION.
-->
      </ACTION>
    </ACTIONS>
  </SUBMISSION>
</SUBMISSION_SET>
```

Please consult the following EGA tool for further support with XML generation:
[Star2XML: tool for converting metadata spreadsheets into XML submission files.](#)

Submit the XMLs

Once both XML files are ready, submit them using the following method:

- Submit XMLs using WEBIN API

For programmatic metadata submissions to the EGA through the Webin API, there are two available submission environments: one for testing and another for production.

Test service URL:

<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/drop-box/submit>

Production service URL:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/drop-box/submit>

The Webin test environment is refreshed daily from the production environment at approximately 03:00 GMT/BST. As a result, any submissions performed in the test environment are temporary and will be automatically removed within 24 hours.

When using the test submission service, the XML receipt will include a message similar to:

"This submission is a TEST submission and will be discarded within 24 hours."

We strongly recommend first validating XML files and testing submission workflows using the Webin test service before proceeding with production submissions or implementing automated submission pipelines for EGA metadata registration.

```
curl -u username:password \  
-F "SUBMISSION=@submission.xml" \  
-F "ANALYSIS=@analysis.xml" \  
"https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/drop-box/submit/"
```

Authentication

Use your **Webin username and password (ega-box-XXXX)**

Test service (Recommended First)

<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/drop-box/submit/>

- The above
- Data is **deleted after 24 hours**
- Safe for testing

Production service

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/drop-box/submit/>

- Permanent submission
- Use only after successful testing
- More information: [Submit the XMLs](#)

After Submission

Once the analysis accessions (e.g., [EGAZ0000100111](#)) have been successfully created, the submission workflow must be completed by registering the remaining required metadata objects: **Dataset**, **Policy**, and **Data Access Committee (DAC)**.

These components define how the data will be grouped, accessed, and governed under controlled access. Registration can be performed using either the [WEBIN UI](#) or the [WEBIN API](#), depending on your preferred workflow.

Need Help?

Contact the EGA Helpdesk for support during submission: [Need Help?](#)

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